

**ADDITIONAL DATA CONCERNING THE SYSTEMATICS AND
THE REMARKABLE RANGES OF THREE SPECIES OF
LANDSNAILS, KNOWN FROM SINTRA**

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Introduction:

Recently PALAZZI (1988) published some interesting notes concerning land-snails collected in Sintra. In the present paper some additional information is provided, especially with regard to the nomenclature and the zoogeographical interest of three of the species listed by PALAZZI. These species are wide-spread, but their ranges are extraordinarily disjunct, with distributional gaps of hundreds or even thousands of kilometres.

For collections the following abbreviations are used: MHNG-Bgt, collection of the late J. R. BOURGUIGNAT in the Muséum d'Histoire Naturelle, Genève, Switzerland; RMNH, Rijksmuseum van Natuurlijke Historie, Leiden, The Netherlands.

Notes:

Carychium ibazoricum Bank & Gittenberger, 1985

(figs. 1-2)

While introducing the name *Auricula gracilis* for a new species, MORELET (1845) apparently overlooked that this name had been preoccupied (even twice in fact). Therefore, BANK & GITTENBERGER (1985: 85) published the *nomen novum* *C. ibazoricum*. With the epithet *ib-azoricum* the occurrence of the species on both the Iberian peninsula and the Azores was indicated.

C. ibazoricum (figs. 1-2; see also PALAZZI, 1988: 18) is characterized conchologically by (1) prominent transverse riblets, (2) a distinct granular microsculpture on both the proto- and the teleoconch (fig. 2), and (3) a sinuous edge of the comparatively long internal part of the parietal lamella (fig. 1). Because *C. ibazoricum* occurs on the Azores with both *C. minimum* Müller, 1774 and *C. tridentatum* (Risso, 1826), these three taxa should be considered separate species.

In the specimen figured by PALAZZI, typical *C. ibazoricum* in shape and sculpture, the internal part of the parietal lamella is (much) less sinuous than it is in our material (fig. 1 shows the opposite extreme). For the moment being this is considered individual variation, comparable to that observed in e.g. *C. tridentatum* (see BANK & GITTENBERGER, 1985: figs. 16-28). In *C. minimum* the edge of the parietal lamella regularly curves around the columella in such a way that (in front view) both its upside and its underside are clearly seen in front of the columella. The specimen figured by PALAZZI clearly differs in this respect.

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Spermodea lamellata (Jeffreys, 1830)

(fig. 3)

This species has been reported from Portugal for the first time, as *Helix spermatia*, by J. DA SILVA E CASTRO (1887: 249), from the woods of Bussaco. GITTENBERGER (1977: fig. 2) figured a possible syntype and compared it with *S. lamellata*, as had been done before already by DA SILVA E CASTRO. The former author provisionally concluded that two species might be involved. However, with additional material of *Spermodea* from Portugal in hand now, collected independently by S. G. A. JAECKEL (in Sintra), H. P. M. G. MENKHORST (in Bussaco) and Th. E. J. RIPKEN (in Bussaco and Sintra), it may be concluded that there is only a single *Spermodea* species in W. Europe, which cannot even be subdivided into subspecies, although its distribution is strikingly disjunct. There are two subranges, separated by a gap of over 2000 km. It has been suggested (SCHLICKUM & TRUC, 1972: 193) that this disjunction dates from the Pleistocene.

GITTENBERGER (1977) apparently overlooked that there is another recent *Spermodea* species, occurring on the Azores and reported from there by BACKHUYS (1975: 111, pl. 7 fig. 22). This species, *S. monas* (Morelet, 1860), can be very easily distinguished from *S. lamellata*, but the two species are clearly congeneric.

Plagyrona placida (Shuttleworth, 1852)

(figs. 4-5)

PALAZZI (1988: 17) listed «*Planogyra sororcula* (Benoit, 1857)» from Sintra. Most probably, however, this record does not concern the true *Gittenbergia sororcula* (see GIUSTI & MANGANELLI, 1986 for notes concerning the generic position of this species), but refers to «*Helix bussacona*», described as new from the woods of Bussaco by DA SILVA E CASTRO (1887: 246). GITTENBERGER (1977: 297) indicated that the species in question had been described before, from Algeria, as *Helix de-beauxiana* by BOURGUIGNAT, 1863: 183, pl. 19 figs. 13-16. Later on WALDÉN (1983: 268) indicated that *Plagyrona placida* (Shuttleworth, 1852) is its correct name.

As far as known at present, *P. placida* has an unusual distributional pattern. The species is known from the Canary islands Hierro, La Palma and Tenerife, as well as from Madeira (WOLLASTON, 1878: 87, 331). GITTENBERGER (1977) summarized the records from Algeria and Portugal. WALDÉN discovered its occurrence in Greece, on the Ionian Island Kerkyra (personal communication). The present author collected shells on this and two more Ionian islands, viz. Ithaki and Kephallinia (= Cephalonia).

P. placida is characterized conchologically by its *Pyramidula*- or *Planogyra*-like general shape, in combination with (1) dominating, narrowly spaced, regular, radial riblets on the teleoconch and (2) a microsculpture of spiral lines and (much) less prominent radial riblets on the protoconch. The shells are fragile. The anatomy of the species is still unknown and its systematic position somewhat uncertain, therefore.

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Figs. 1-2. *Carychium ibazoricum* Bank & Gittenberger [1, x 70; 2, x 200]; Azores, São Miguel, Pico Grande, NE. of Ponta Delgada; W. Backhuys leg. (RMNH); SEM photographs by J. H. W. Krom.

Fig. 3. *Spermodea lamellata* (Jeffreys) [actual width 2.1 mm]; Portugal, Sintra; S. G. A. Jaeckel leg. (RMNH); SEM photograph by J. H. W. Krom.

Figs. 4-5. *Plagyrona placida* (Shuttleworth), syntype *debeauxiana* Bourguignat [actual width 2.0 mm; detail of the embryonic whorls, x 240]; Portugal, Coimbra?; leg. (MHNG-Bgt); SEM photograph by J. H. W. Krom.

Figs. 4-5. *Plagyrona placida* (Shuttleworth), syntype *debeauxiana* Bourguignat [actual width 2.0 mm; detail of the embryonic whorls, x 240]; Portugal, Coimbra;? leg. (MHNG-Bgt); SEM photograph by J. H. W. Krom.

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